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Geospatial Assessment of Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) & Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) Opportunities in Brazil

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The RCGI – Research Centre for Greenhouse Gas Innovation has emerged as a global centre for advanced studies on mitigating greenhouse gas emissions and energy transition. Based at the University of São Paulo (USP) and funded through a partnership between the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP) and the private sector, the centre is a reference in supporting high-level scientific research for the development of the energy sector. Its activities are based on three pillars: research, innovation, and knowledge dissemination.

Research Centre for
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Welcome words

This Report is the result of a collaborative and interdisciplinary journey that began in 2020 with a bold question: how does society perceive and engage with the technologies shaping our low-carbon future? It was born from the initial brainstorming that led to Project 70 – Social Perception and Science Diplomacy on Technological Transitions towards a Low-Carbon Society, a key initiative of the Advocacy Programme at RCGI-USP, developed within the Research Centre for Greenhouse Gas Innovation, currently celebrating its tenth anniversary.

At the heart of Project 70 lies the recognition that energy transitions are not purely technical challenges - they are deeply social. Public perception, cultural context, political trust, and social engagement have become decisive factors in the adoption of climate technologies such as Carbon Capture & Storage (CCS), Bioenergy with Carbon Capture & Storage (BECCS), Carbon Capture & Utilisation (CCU), Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), and Greenhouse Gas (GHG) reduction technologies. Yet, in Brazil, these social dimensions remain largely underexplored in energy planning and policy.

This work seeks to provide a framework that helps fill part of this gap. It introduces a novel overlaying methodology that overlays industrial GHG emissions, CO₂ transport infrastructure, and geological storage capacity to identify priority regions for CCS and BECCS deployment in Brazil. Grounded in the understanding that societal perception must be examined within its local context, the Report offers a spatial lens to explore where decarbonisation technologies could be implemented while also laying the groundwork for future research on how these technologies may be perceived by the communities in those identified areas in Brazil.

Integrating disciplines such as sociology, psychology, anthropology, geography, geology, physics, history, political science, and economics, Project 70 addresses complex questions around trust, awareness, resistance, and acceptance. It aims not only to understand public views, but to co-create tools and strategies that help decision-makers in government, industry, and civil society act with legitimacy and foresight.

Structured across five workstreams—WS1: Social Perception; WS2: Science Diplomacy; WS3: Socio-Historic and Geographic Transitions; WS4: Sociophysics and Immersive Experiences; and WS5: Innovation & Tech Transfer—the project combines scientific rigour with creative methods such as digital twins, citizen science, art-science and the overlaying mapping proposed in this study. As part of WS3, this work is both a scientific output and an invitation to deepen dialogue at the intersection of science, society, and sustainability.

We thank all the researchers, collaborators, and communities who made this work possible. May it serve as a guide and an inspiration for advancing a just, informed, and low-carbon future for Brazil and beyond.

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Executive summary

This report is part of a broader study conducted by a multidisciplinary team from the Research Centre for Greenhouse Gas Innovation (RCGI), within the scope of Project 70, titled "Social Perception and Scientific Diplomacy on Technological Transitions towards a Low-Carbon Society (Applications Associated with NBS, CCU, GHG, and BECCS)."

The primary objective of the project is to understand and manage the formation and evolution of perceptions, attitudes, resistance, and other subjective characteristics among the Brazilian population regarding climate and technological issues for cleaner energy. This includes the perception of all stakeholders, from government representatives, policy makers, industry executives, investors, academia, media and civil society about the developments of applications associated with NBS (Nature-Based Solutions), CCUS (Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage), GHG (Greenhouse Gases), and BECCS (Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage).

Focusing on CCS and BECCS, the report acknowledges that global research and implementation of these technologies remain in development. Their feasibility and pace of adoption vary significantly by country, depending on local contexts. Nonetheless, CCS and BECCS are seen as essential for decarbonising hard-to-abate sectors, including steel, cement, refineries, thermoelectric power, and biofuel production (CACHOLA et al., 2023).

In Brazil, the primary GHG emissions come from the Land Use Change and Forestry and Agriculture sectors. However, in certain locations, such as the State of São Paulo and State of Espírito Santo, industrial GHG emissions are significant. Hence, understanding the context of the country's GHG emissions, including its level of industrialization and energy mix, is crucial. Therefore, this report begins by contextualizing these analytical elements to contribute to a feasibility analysis of Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) and BECCS in Brazil.

Based on this premise and drawing from existing scientific literature on CCS and BECCS technology across various technological and geographic contexts, this study examines local GHG emissions by industrial sector, available transportation infrastructure, and Brazil's geological capacity to store carbon dioxide (CO₂). Therefore, the primary aim of this report is to devise a methodology incorporating overlapping geographic and environmental data on GHG emissions, focusing on industrial emissions amenable to CCS technology for local decarbonisation in the Brazilian context. It then examines the historical, demographic, and territorial characteristics of these priority regions to support future analyses of local engagement and social acceptance.

The report ultimately proposes a methodology that overlays data layers of industrial GHG emissions, CO₂ transport infrastructure, and storage potential to empirically locate key hubs for CCS and BECCS deployment. It then explores the historical and demographic characteristics of these priority regions.

Greenhouse gas emissions in Brazil

There are many factors that determine the global climate, stemming from both natural and human origins (IPCC, 1990). One of the most critical factors is the greenhouse effect, which partially traps the sun's rays that would otherwise be reflected by the Earth's surface, thus maintaining a warmer planetary temperature (IPCC, 1990). The main contributors to human-origin GHGs are CO₂, methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), and chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) (IPCC, 1990).

For clarity, the concept of relative Global Warming Potential (GWP) was developed to account for the differing lifetimes of gases in the atmosphere (IPCC, 1990). Typically, inventories utilize the common unit of carbon dioxide equivalent (CO₂e), where one ton of CH₄ (of fossil origin) is equivalent to 29.8 tons of CO₂e, and one ton of N₂O is equivalent to 273 tons of CO₂e (IPCC, 2021).

In Brazil, the CO₂ emission inventory is divided into 5 sectors (MCTIC, 2017) (see Figure 1):

- Energy: CO₂e emissions due to the fuel combustion and fugitive emissions of oil, gas, and coal industries.
- Industrial Process: CO₂e emissions due to the industrial process in the plants that are not the result of fuel combustion.
- Agriculture: CO₂e emissions due to the enteric fermentation of cattle, manure management animals, agricultural soils, rice cultivation, and burning of agricultural residues.
- Land Use Change and Forests: emissions and removals resulting from variations of the amount of carbon, whether from plant biomass or from the soil, considering all possible transitions between different uses.
- Waste Treatment: CO₂e emissions from the disposal and incineration of solid waste and from the treatment of effluents, both domestic/commercial, and industrial.

Figure 1 | 2020 Brazilian sectoral GHG emissions.

Source: SEEG* (GWP-AR5 Gg CO₂e).

*The Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Removals Estimation System (SEEG) is linked to Brazilian non-profit organizations, which measures the country's emissions through a methodology published in the journal Nature, in 2018 (DE AZEVEDO et al., 2018). Since the government of Brazil has not published issuance reports since 2016, SEEG is used as the main source for this purpose. For all tables and graphs, we are considering net emissions, which consider removals. If we evaluate only gross emissions, activities related to land use largely lead emissions.

Greenhouse gas emissions in Brazil

According to the last SEEG report, released and seen in Table 1, Brazilian emissions in 2020 increase in emissions from activities related to land use change (111%) (compared to 2019), mainly due to forest deforestation. In 2020 there was also a drop in the energy sector (-5%) which can be explained by the reduction in transport due to the Covid-19 pandemic (POTENZA et al., 2021).

Category	2018	2019	2020
Energy	405,702	409,113	387,413
Industrial Process	101,009	99,270	99,733
Agriculture	563,242	565,230	578,848
Land Use Change and Forests	178,839	323,857	334,864
Waste Treatment	88,308	89,644	91,235

Data from industrial processes and waste treatment show little change in these emissions in these 3 years, while agriculture increased by 2.5% between 2019 and 2020. These results placed activities associated with soil (land use itself and agriculture) as the central point of Brazilian emissions (POTENZA et al., 2021).

Table 1 | Brazilian emissions from 2018 – 2020.
Source: SEEG (2021) (GWP-AR5 Gg CO₂e).

The data from 1990 to 2020 (see Figure 2) allows an analysis of the historical evolution of Brazilian emissions. The peak and fall of emissions in the country are mainly associated with the lack of control over land use, however, other emissions have shown considerable increases over the years.

Figure 2 | Brazilian net emissions from 1990 to 2020.
Source: SEEG (GWP-AR5 Gg CO₂e).

GHG emissions from the Brazilian energy sector

In Table 2 it is possible to see which subsectors make up the sum of emissions from the Brazilian energy sector. It is visible that from 1990 to 2020, transport (includes air, road, rail and water transport models) was the main subsector that contributed the most to CO₂ emissions (SEEG, 2021; MCTIC, 2017). The second largest contributor of CO₂ emissions – in the energy sector – has been the industrial subsector (SEEG, 2021). The industrial subsector comprises the manufacture of iron and steel, ferroalloys, chemicals, non-metallics, pulp and paper, food and beverage, cement, mining, textiles, ceramics, and other industries (MCTIC, 2017).

The energy mix in Brazil comprises a significant 48% contribution from renewable sources, a markedly higher proportion when compared to the global energy mix, which is composed of just 14% from renewable generation (EPE, 2021). Biomass and hydropower emerge as prominent contributors within the realm of renewable energy sources. Sugarcane ethanol is extensively employed as a transportation fuel, while the electrical grid primarily relies on hydroelectric power plants (see Figure 3).

Activity	Sum from 1990 to 2020 Gg CO ₂ e	% of the total	2020 Gg CO ₂ e	% of the total
Production of Fuels (fugitive emissions)	473,270	4.70%	20,525	5.30%
Emissions from Burning Fuels:				
Agricultural	507,967	5.05%	20,536	5.30%
Commercial	62,790	0.62%	1,644	0.42%
Electricity Generation (Public Service)	766,823	7.62%	33,179	8.56%
Industrial	1,940,294	19.28%	61,491	15.87%
Not identified	2,797	0.03%	-	0.00%
Fuel production	807,516	8.02%	35,992	9.29%
Public	43,836	0.44%	852	0.22%
Residential	786,104	7.81%	27,704	7.15%
Transport	4,671,938	46.43%	185,491	47.88%
Total Energy	10,063,336		387,413	

Table 2 | CO₂ emissions from the Brazilian energy sector. 1990-2020.

Source: (GWP-AR5 Gg CO₂e) SEEG (2021).

Figure 3 | Energy sources used in Brazil.

Source: (EPE, 2021).

CCS, BECCUS and the SDGs

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), sometimes referred to as the Global Goals, were enacted by the United Nations in 2015 as a global call to action to eradicate poverty, safeguard the environment, and guarantee that by the year 2030, peace and prosperity will be experienced by everyone. The 17 SDGs understand that development must balance social, economic, and environmental sustainability and that actions in one area will have an impact on results in others.

The SDGs must be achieved in every setting, and this requires the creativity, knowledge, technology, and financial resources of the entire population. Thus, low carbon technologies must be thought of in parallel to the SDGs, which rectifies the relevance of understanding how these issues meet.

Figure 5 | Venn diagram showing the intersection between papers published on SDGs and on CCS and BECCUS.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

For the case of this atlas, we sought to understand how the SDGs and the CCS/BECCUS correlate in the scientific literature, to map this relationship and understand how to apply this knowledge to our work. We searched the Scopus database for academic papers to understand how these low-carbon solutions are associated with the SDGs and, more specifically, with which SDGs. In the Scopus database, 18 documents correlating these themes were found (see Figure 5).

However, the strength of the correlation between these themes is diverse, and it is common for the topic of SDGs to be treated only as an a priori attraction of low-carbon technologies. Still, the alignment of these fields tends to be overlooked (or, more specifically, disconnected) in the evolution of decarbonisation research.

One observation that arises from this research is that the CCS and BECCUS technologies seem to be much more connected with the Paris agreement (251 documents correlate the topics directly) than with the SDGs (18 documents associate the topics).

The portion of articles on CCS and BECCUS that directly address the SDGs is very limited (0.24% of total) and when considering the use of keywords used in the articles that correlate these themes, the most frequently cited words are sustainable development (12 mentions) and carbon capture (10 mentions). Figure 6 shows the relations between keywords.

CCS, BECCUS and the SDGs

Considering the case of this Report, we note that the work we have done correlates with the 9 SDGs of the 17, which are mentioned below. In our work, we identified the correlation with SDGs that concern societal, economic, and environmental aspects and pointed out the most relevant.

Regarding the Societal aspects (see Figure 8), SDGs 3 (Good Health and Well-being), 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation) and 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) are the most directly correlated.

Figure 8 | Societal goals.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Regarding the Economic aspects (see Figure 9), SDGs 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), 9 (Industry Innovation and Infrastructure) and 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) are the most directly correlated.

Figure 9 | Economical goals.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Regarding the Environmental aspects (see Figure 10), SDGs 13 (Climate Action), 14 (Life Below Water) and 15 (Life on Land) are the most directly correlated.

Figure 10 | Environmental goals.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

It is evident that all of these SDGs can be impacted either positively or negatively by CCS/BECCUS, and critical analysis is needed on a case-by-case basis. For example, CCS can both help the climate issue by reducing the level of greenhouse gases (GHG) in the atmosphere but can also cause risk to marine life with CO₂ leakage. Furthermore, the same SDG can be impacted both positively and negatively (marine life benefits by reducing GHGs in the atmosphere). This brief example reiterates the complexity and need for deeper study of each case.

It is also important to note that other SDGs may be impacted by these technologies, requiring further studies.

Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS)

Carbon Capture is a technology that removal CO_2 from smokestacks of industries and thermal power plants (IPCC, 2013). The CO_2 captured can be stored, a technology called Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS), or used as raw material, a process called Carbon Capture and Use (CCU) (Arning et al., 2019), or both alternatives can be adopted (CCUS) (AHMED et al., 2021).

CCU comprises a set of technologies, where CO_2 is captured and converted to be used such as raw material to produce plastic, chemicals, fuels, and construction materials (ARNING et al., 2019).

CCS involves capturing CO_2 from industrial flue gases and then transporting it for injection into safe geological reservoirs. The capture technologies include: (i) post-combustion; (ii) pre-combustion; (iii) oxy-fuel combustion, and (iv) chemical loop combustion (FENNELL et al., 2021; TAPIA et al., 2018). Storage includes geological formations such as depleted oil or gas reservoirs, inaccessible coal deposits, and saline aquifers (RISSMAN et al., 2020; TAPIA et al., 2018)

Regarding the Environmental aspects (see Figure 10), SDGs 13 (Climate Action), 14 (Life Below Water) and 15 (Life on Land) are the most directly correlated.

Figure 11 | Outline of carbon capture and use (CCU) or storage (CCS) technology.

Source: Elaborated by the authors based on [ENERGYNOW MEDIA, 2024](#).

BECCS - Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage

As with CCS, bioenergy is considered one of the most efficient technologies for global decarbonisation projects. Bioenergy is regarded as a clean energy source due to the significant amounts of CO₂ captured and absorbed during biomass growth. Through the process of photosynthesis, biomass can maintain constant levels of CO₂ emissions within the natural carbon cycle, using abundant bio-based raw materials. BECCS enhances this process by enabling the capture of CO₂ emissions during biomass combustion, allowing for the reuse or storage of carbon using CCUS technology (CIOTTA et al., 2020). BECCS also presents technological and cost-saving potential. For instance, in the ethanol production process, the off-gas from the fermentation of sugar is 99% pure CO₂, significantly more concentrated than the off-gas from power plants and refineries (GEF, 2009). This renders BECCS highly competitive, as a current challenge for CCS lies in the expensive nature of CO₂ capture and treatment, typically involving complex techniques and significant energy consumption for carbon separation and concentration.

Although the BECCUS technology is a promising option for the decarbonisation of the energy sector, the Global CCS Institute has pointed out four main challenges for its wide scale deployment (Global CCS Institute, 2019):

- The productivity and resource requirements for the different types of land and biomass vary significantly, leading to the need of extensive areas.
- Crop production can involve land clearing, which may reduce or even reverse the targeted carbon removal potential.
- Competition or overlapping with land for forest creation or food production, leading to significant changes in ecosystems.
- High demand of water for irrigation and fertilizers.

Figure 12 | Outline of carbon capture and use (CCU) or storage (CCS) technology. [Source: Elaborated by the authors ENERGINOW MEDIA, 2024.](#)

Data processing: layers overlay

The methodology used in this report involves overlaying geographic information, considering GHG emissions, infrastructure, and CO₂ storage potential. The figure below briefly illustrates the methodology applied in this report.

To group the data analytically, the Qgis software was used. The step-by-step in the Qgis software is attached to this document and can be seen in the final pages. There are a total of 21 data treatment and homogenization steps, both for CCS and for the calculation of the BECCUS potential.

While the CCS data group the data already quite exposed, for the calculation of the BECCS hubs, a series of extra calculations were necessary, making it highly recommended to access the annex to visualise the equations performed.

The calculation of emissions associated with BECCS required, for example, consulting the literature on emissions from different types of biofuels applied in Brazilian territory, which are biodiesel, biogas, anhydrous ethanol, and hydrous ethanol. As a next step, the use of these fuels per municipality was sought.

Figure 13 | Methodological procedures (Elaborated by the authors).

Data processing: sources

The **geological capacity for CO₂ storage** defined in this study relied heavily on the significant contributions made by Ciotta et al. (2021).

Thus, the application of Ciotta's methodology followed three steps:

i) global feasibility of sedimentary basins based on Bachu (2003), Gibson-Poole et al. (2008) and Ketzer et al. (2015).

iii) calculation of CO₂ storage capacity for oil and gas fields according to the CSFL and USDOE methods (Bachu et al., 2007; Goodman et al., 2011).

iii) analysis of the presence of available infrastructure and proximity to emitting sources.

The **infrastructure data** were collected from the Energy Research Company (EPE) database. The georeferenced zoning information base, BIZROG (acronym for National Oil and Gas Resource Zoning Information Base) follows the 2017–2019 cycle update. The Supply Infrastructure that is part of the Zoning information base was prepared to incorporate the main elements that geographically represent the processing, storage and transport of oil, derivatives and natural gas (EPE, 2019).

The pipeline routes considered in this work are those available in the current Brazilian network, and new routes were not suggested.

It is worth highlighting that the infrastructure criterion solely considers the availability of gas pipelines, and we solely utilized CO₂ emissions data from municipalities as a means of delineating zones of greatest interest.

The CO₂ emission data per municipality studied came from the SEEG, an initiative of the Climate Observatory, which comprises the production of annual estimates of GHG in Brazil (SEEG, 2021). The GHG Emissions and Removals Estimates are generated according to the guidelines of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), based on the methodology of the Brazilian Inventories of Anthropogenic GHG Emissions and Removals, prepared by the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation (MCTI), and on data obtained from government reports, institutes, research centres, sector entities and non-governmental organizations (de Azevedo et al., 2018; SEEG, 2021).

Lastly, this case study **only considers stationary emissions data from energy generation (fuel burning) and industrial processes (e.g., refining, cement production, iron production, ammonia production, ethanol production, among others).**

Data processing: geological storage consideration

About the theoretical geological potential of Brazil to store carbon, there are studies that mapped the Brazilian regions, including generating an Atlas on the CCS in Brazil, as can be seen in (KETZER et al., 2016). From a geological point of view, 4 important characteristics are conceptualized:

- 1) Occurrence of coal deposits.
- 2) Active production of hydrocarbons.
- 3) Existence of saline formations data.
- 4) Theoretical capacity for storing CO₂.

Geologically, Brazil constitutes the larger part of the South American shelf, which is the most stable of the South American tectonic plate that extends into the Atlantic Ocean. This platform is formed by ancient igneous and metamorphic rocks formed during the Precambrian period (over 590 million from years ago).

Over the millions of years, subsequent complex movements of the earth's crust created a series of basins (depressions) in various parts of Brazil. It is these basins that allowed the accumulation of thick sequences of sedimentary rocks, which include the vast deposits of oil, gas and coal.

There are 31 sedimentary basins in the Brazilian territory, totaling an area of approximately 6.4 million km². 25% of this territory is located at sea.

Although there are studies looking for evaluations on the geological storage potential of Brazilian sedimentary basins, especially in the Paraná basin, in general, this potential is a major knowledge gap in almost all sedimentary basins in the country (Abraham-A. & Tassinari, 2021; Musarra et al., 2022)

However, in marine sedimentary basins, mainly in those where oil and gas extraction already take place, there are several mapping studies of geological storage potential. **For this reason, this study sought these study bases, and all calculated potential considered only the marine geological basins.**

The use of for CCS and BECCS for these sedimentary basins also has an important technical and economic argument: using these locations for carbon storage purposes can avoid the decommissioning of depleted oil wells, and even using existing infrastructure, or at least of the existing route of transport infrastructures interconnecting the onshore/offshore environment.

According to other studies on the feasibility of CCS, even in basins classified as "low prospecting", it is possible to consider the use of reservoirs, as the focus is different from an assessment for the extraction of some type of hydrocarbon (CIOTTA et al., 2021). Thus, the proposed criteria followed Bachu (2003) and Gibson-Poole et al. (2008).

The feasibility in oil fields was also evaluated, in this case, using criteria already established by (Bachu, 2000; Bradshaw et al., 2007; IPCC, 2005; Tomić et al., 2018). The estimation of the CO₂ storage capacity in oil and gas reservoirs follows the fundamental premise that the volume previously occupied by the produced hydrocarbons becomes available for CO₂ storage (BACHU et al., 2007; CSFL, 2008).

Transport infrastructure and geologic storage

Source: CIOTTA ET AL., 2021; EPE, 2018; IBGE, 2020; SEEG, 2018.

Map 1 | Transport infrastructure and geologic store.

Study layers - Brazilian industry emissions (CCS)

An advanced search was carried out based on the scientific works of Scopus to find the industrial sectors with the greatest prospects for implementing the CCS. Seven key sectors were found:

- (i) cement plants,
- (ii) chemical plants,
- (iii) glass plants,
- (iv) steel plants,
- (v) power plants,
- (vi) pulp and paper plants
- (vii) refineries.

With data from the Gas Emissions Estimation System (SEEG) - CO2 emissions by the municipality and economic sector were disclosed - and from the advanced search carried out previously, the correlation of the data allowed the elaboration of the geographic atlas with potential for CCS in Brazil.

As a first result, the region with the greatest potential for CCS implementation in Brazil was found, the municipality of Serra - Espírito Santo. In Serra there is a steel mill belonging to the Arcelor Mittal company and data collection was also carried out to collect information about the municipality. Other Brazilian centers with prospects for implementing the CCS were also found and will be analyzed.

Figure 14 | Industry sector with the greatest prospects for implementing CCS.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Cement Facilities

CO₂e emissions from the cement industry play a significant role in global emissions, with this production process accounting for 22% of emissions from the industrial sector in Brazil in 2020, amounting to 21,985 Gg CO₂e (SEEG, 2021). Specifically, emissions from the cement industry resulting from fuel combustion amount to 13,020 Gg CO₂e, representing 22% of industry emissions from fuel combustion (SEEG, 2021).

In global terms, the majority of carbon emissions from cement production, approximately 90%, stem from two main sources: the generation of thermal energy and the decarbonation of limestone. During the industrial process, limestone undergoes a chemical reaction, releasing CO₂ for clinker production. It is estimated that the generation of thermal energy and the decarbonation of limestone are responsible for 40% and 50% of emissions, respectively. The remaining 10% is distributed among transportation and electricity consumption at the factory (ABDI, 2012).

Source: IBGE, 2020; SEEG, 2018.

Map 2 | Cement facilities carbon emissions.

Power Plants

While Brazil's electricity generation primarily relies on renewable sources, thermal power plants are necessary to ensure system reliability, especially to address the seasonality of renewables and in regions lacking connectivity to the national grid (SIN) (EPE, 2021). These plants' locations, measured by their CO₂e emissions, can be observed in the accompanying map.

SEEG conducts specific monitoring of emissions from Brazilian electricity generation. An analysis spanning 2009 to 2018 revealed that the predominant emitting fuels were natural gas (50%), followed by natural coal (32.5%), and oil (17.5%).

The years of higher emissions from Brazilian thermoelectric plants are justified by the drought, as these periods intensify CO₂e emissions by increasing the burning of fuels in thermal plants, also adding to the financial value of energy generation (EPE, 2021).

Source: IBGE, 2020; SEEG, 2018.

Map 3 | Power plants carbon emissions.

Refineries

In 2020, GHG emissions from oil refining reached 24.500 Gg CO₂e, which corresponds to 65% of emissions from fuel production (SEEG, 2021). Petroleum refining is a set of processes aimed at transforming crude oil (petroleum) into derivatives of commercial value such as diesel, gasoline, liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), kerosene, among others.

As visible on the Map 4, oil refining in Brazil is centered in regions close to the marine coast, except for a refinery in the Amazon region.

Source: IBGE, 2020; SEEG, 2018.

Map 4 | Refineries carbon emissions.

Iron and Steel Facilities

GHG emissions from the production of pig iron and steel are a significant global concern. In Brazil, this sector accounted for 39% of all industrial emissions in 2020, totaling 38,850 Gg CO₂e. Additionally, the combustion of fuel throughout this process, including transportation, emitted an additional 6,700 Gg CO₂e in 2020.

The production of iron and steel and iron in 2020 represented more than 80% (38,849 Gg CO₂e) of the emissions associated with metal production (total of 46,292 Gg CO₂e). Metal production includes aluminum, iron and steel, ferroalloys, magnesium, and other non-ferrous production.

Source: IBGE, 2020; SEEG, 2018.

Map 5 | Iron and steel facilities carbon emissions.

Other Industries Facilities

Other emissions stem from the use of fuel for energy production across various industries. The total of these emissions in 2020 reached 4,240 Gg CO₂e, predominantly from the combustion of petroleum coke and dry natural gas. Over the years, these emissions have been declining, primarily attributed to the reduction of coal burning in certain industries.

Source: IBGE, 2020; SEEG, 2018.

Map 6 | Other industry facilities carbon emissions.

BEECS - emissions from the Brazilian biofuel industry

Biofuels play a large role in the Brazilian energy matrix. In 2021, sugarcane derivatives alone accounted for 16.4% of the entire domestic energy supply (EPE, 2022).

Derivatives from sugar cane are the main producers of ethanol, which is widespread in Brazil as a transport fuel. In 2021, national ethanol production decreased by - 8.3%, still impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic, reaching an amount of 29.9 million m³ (EPE, 2022). Of this total, 61.4% refer to hydrous ethanol: 18.3 million m³. The production of anhydrous ethanol, which is mixed with gasoline, increased by 11%, totaling 11.6 million m³ (EPE, 2022).

Although there have been incentives for mixing sugarcane ethanol with gasoline since 1931 in Brazil, this fuel became widely disseminated as an alternative to the world oil crises of the 1970s (CARVALHO, 2011).

The Brazilian government started to increase the mixture of ethanol from sugar cane in gasoline, which also proved to be a good environmental solution, reducing emissions (SOARES et al., 2009). This is because ethanol has a positive energy balance, emitting less carbon into the atmosphere compared to gasoline (CORTEZ, 2016).

Brazilian public policies aimed at sugarcane fuels, Proálcool, are considered one of the most successful programs aimed at biofuels in the world (OLIVEIRA and ZANIN, 2015). Currently, Brazil is the second largest producer of ethanol in the world, behind only the United States, and the largest producer of sugarcane in the world (VIDAL, 2021).

The strategy of mixing biofuels with fossil fuels was also adopted by Brazil for Biodiesel (ANP, 2018). However, this fuel does not originate from sugarcane, being made mainly from soybean oil (D'AGOSTO, 2015).

In 2022, the percentage of biodiesel added to Brazilian diesel was 10%, but there are schedules aimed at raising this level (CARREGOSA, 2022). In addition, to developing this national industry, there is also an environmental appeal in this policy since this fuel also minimizes overall diesel emissions.

Finally, another biofuel investigated in this Report, biomethane, also has a strong association with GHG mitigation, mainly in the transport sector. The use of these fuels in vehicles can reduce pollutant emissions by up to 90%, compared to gasoline. This occurs because its use prevents the release of atmospheric CH₄, reducing GHG emissions (CETESB, 2017).

Biomethane is a mixture of CH₄, CO₂ and small amounts of other gases produced by the anaerobic digestion of organic matter in an oxygen-free environment. In the year 2020, 60% of the plants in operation and under development injected biomethane into the gas distribution network worldwide, 20% of the remainder was provided as fuel for vehicles, and a small percentage remaining was disseminated in various uses, making all these mentioned processes a little more sustainable, when using this renewable fuel (IEA 2020).

Biodiesel Plants

Biodiesel plays a crucial role in the energy transition as an important renewable fuel. It can be produced from various renewable sources, including babassu, canola, crambe, palm, turnip, sunflower, jatropha, lupine, soybean, peanut, castor, macaúba, animal fat, used cooking oil, and photosynthetic algae (MONTEIRO et al., 2018).

Brazil ranks as the second-largest producer of biodiesel globally, trailing only behind the United States. The increasing production of biodiesel involves other significant contributors such as Germany, Indonesia, and Argentina. Collectively, the European Union stands as the largest producer and consumer of biodiesel (MONTEIRO et al., 2018).

Source: ANP, 2022; IBGE, 2020.

Map 7 | Biodiesel maximum daily production.

Biomethane Plants

According to Junior et al. (2022), Brazil has the greatest biogas production potential, due to its extensive agro-industrial production and the fact that the country has a population of more than 210 million inhabitants. In the sugar-energy sector alone, the Brazilian Association of Biogas and Biomethane (ABiogás) reports a biogas production potential of 41.4 billion m³ per year.

This fuel can be used in vehicles, can generate electricity or even as local thermal demand in industries and other uses. This enormous potential attracts more and more perspectives for the development of technologies aimed at this purpose. However, less than 2% of Brazil's cited potential is currently achieved, indicating that biomethane is still in need of much improvement and visibility.

Source: ANP, 2022; IBGE, 2020.

Map 8 | Biomethane maximum daily production.

Biomethane Plants

According to Gonçalves et al. (2018), hydrated ethanol is a fuel that is widely consumed in Brazil, being one of the main fuels to diversify the fossil energy matrix for the automotive fuel industry. It comprises about 95% to 96% ethanol and 4 to 4.9% water. Its attractiveness is due to the lower national cost compared to gasoline.

Ethanol can be obtained through the distillation of fermented organic products, such as sucrose from the broth (sugar), with Brazil being the main producer of ethanol from sugarcane. This industry is constantly looking for efficiencies, and the BECCUS would be a way to make it even more sustainable. Currently, the by-products and waste generated can be used to co-generate electricity, manufacture animal feed and fertilizer for crops.

Source: ANP, 2022; IBGE, 2020.

Map 9 | Hydrous ethanol maximum daily production.

Anhydrous Ethanol Plants

Anhydrous ethanol is the version of this product in a practically pure state, with amounts of water lower than 0.5%. And this version of ethanol that is added to gasoline, which is a Brazilian public policy that guarantees the market for this fuel.

As already mentioned, this policy has a lot to do with dealing with oil crises, but in addition, the mixture of anhydrous ethanol in gasoline can improve the combustion of this fuel, and under normal conditions of supply of sugar and ethanol fuels (CARPIO and SOUZA, 2017).

Currently, the mixture of anhydrous ethanol in gasoline can reach up to 27%.

Source: ANP, 2022; IBGE, 2020.

Map 10 | Anhydrous ethanol maximum daily production.

Carbon Capture Potential

Source: CIOTTA ET AL., 2021; EPE, 2018; IBGE, 2020; SEEG, 2018.

Map 11 | Brazilian carbon capture potential.

Hubs of Carbon Capture Potential

Map 12 | Brazilian carbon capture potential.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Serra - Espírito Santo

Carbon Capture and Storage

9,40
CO₂ capture potential

81,59%
Emissions local decrease

data in MtCO₂e, 2018.

Figure 15 | Dashboard of Serra, Espírito Santo.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Serra – ES: Greater potential for CCS

Serra, located in the state of Espírito Santo, is the Brazilian municipality with the highest industrial emission, and in the overall picture is the 14th largest emission (SEEG, 2021). The large emission is associated with the production of steel, which is the main economic activity of the municipality.

Serra has the largest population in the state of Espírito Santo, with 536,765 inhabitants, according to a 2021 estimate by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics – IBGE (IBGE, 2021). Founded in 1556, the municipality had a small population and a rural-based economy until the 1970s, when it underwent strong industrialization, mainly through the installation of Tubarão steel company - CST (Current ArcelorMittal) (Lima, 2017).

Currently Serra – ES is the 48th largest Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Brazil, and the second largest in the state of Espírito Santo, behind the capital Vitória (IBGE, 2021).

The proximity to the capital Vitória, which has a great infrastructure development due to the port, railway line and oil extraction on the coast, are factors that enhance the CCS in Serra, in addition to the high industrial GHG emissions.

Serra does not lead any good demographic item in his state, but is among the first places in relation to the percentage of the employed population.

Education in the municipality has a relatively low enrolment, and its enrollment rate in 2010 (6 to 14 years old) was 96.9%, ranked 3751st (out of 5570 municipalities) in the country and 57th in the state (out of 78 municipalities).

The worst requirement assessed in Serra is the population exposed to risk, which is consistent with measuring the risk of disasters such as landslides, floods, and flash floods. Serra is the 8th city in Brazil with the highest risk, and the first in Espírito Santo.

Regarding the company that manages the steel plant, ArcelorMittal, there is a plan presented to reduce CO₂, however, CCS is not a technology that appears in the decarbonisation repertoire suggested by the company.

ArcelorMittal is a multinational industrial conglomerate of steel companies based in Luxembourg, being the largest steel producer in the world. Its largest unit in Brazil is precisely the Tubarão unit, in Serra -ES (ARCELORMITTAL, 2022). This unit is self-sufficient in electricity, and uses the gases generated in its production process, with an internal generation equivalent to the consumption of about 1 million people a year.

The group is committed to being carbon neutral by 2050, and in Brazil the plan is to reduce emissions by 10% by 2030, in relation to the 2020 sustainability report. By 2030, the corporation has defined that it will work on improving existing processes, and later will seek disruptive technologies (INSTITUTO AÇO BRASIL, 2022). The improvement of processes is consistent with energy efficiency projects, use of charcoal in blast furnaces (fixing carbon in replanting), greater use of natural gas, and mainly, use of steel from scrap, reducing the intensity of CO₂ emission (ARCELORMITTAL, 2022).

Regarding the 'disruptive' technologies, which will be used after 2030, one of the main focuses is related to a pilot project at the Hamburg plant - Germany, which aims to use hydrogen from clean energy as a substitute for fossil carbon in the reduction process of iron ore (INSTITUTO AÇO BRASIL, 2022). Other technologies mentioned are the possibility of converting process emissions into new energy sources, such as converting charcoal residues into biofuel, or using the gases generated in the blast furnaces to produce ethanol (ARCELORMITTAL, 2022)

Espírito Santo - Decarbonisation Targets

The State of Espírito Santo instituted the State Policy on Climate Change - PEMC in 2010, and since 2020 it has a permanent forum for taking actions aimed at net zero 2050. Espírito Santo develops a GHG Emissions Neutralization Plan, which is not yet available, but already has previews published here.

The forecast is that in February 2024 the State will publish a final version of the plan, after collective construction with stakeholders.

In the last decades the emission profile of Espírito Santo has changed significantly. The drop in deforestation, together with the growth in energy and industrial emissions, made these last sectors the main emitters. Today, Espírito Santo has the emission profile of industrialized locations, such as Europe, and will have to seek different decarbonisation strategies compared to Brazil, which focuses on land use and agriculture.

Figure 16 | GHG emissions in the state of Espírito Santo - Brazil (1990-2020) by sector.
Source: GHG emissions neutralization plan of Espírito Santo state - 2022.

São Gonçalo do Amarante - Ceará

Carbon Capture and Storage

4,26
CO₂ capture potential

86,31%
Emissions local decrease

data in MtCO₂e, 2018.

Figure 17 | Dashboard of São Gonçalo, Ceará.
Source: Elaborated by the authors.

São Gonçalo do Amarante - CE

São Gonçalo do Amarante is a municipality in the state of Ceará, has a population of approximately 50,000 inhabitants, and the largest GHG emission in that state (SEEG, 2019). Emissions are recent, having as main point the installation of Porto do Pecém, inaugurated in 2002.

The port attracted steel mills, and the emissions were potentiated by the energy shortage of this steel industry, which needed natural coal thermal power plants and natural gas to supply its energy demand. The municipality also has a wind farm in Taíba, which has 5 MW of installed capacity.

The installation of this industrial and logistical complex allowed São Gonçalo do Amarante to exceed the emissions of the state capital - Fortaleza, which has a population 54 times larger -. But it is also this infrastructure that can develop CCS more easily in this location than in other regions of the country.

Founded in 2008, Companhia Siderúrgica do Pecém (CSP) is a binational joint venture formed by Brazilian Vale (50% stake) - one of the world's largest iron ore mining companies -, South Korean Dongkuk (30%) - world's largest buyer of steel slabs -, and Posco (20%) - 4th largest steelmaker in the world and first in South Korea -. With an investment of around US\$ 5.4 billion, CSP is the first integrated plant in the Northeast and the thirtieth installed in Brazil.

CSP's installed capacity is 3 million tons of steel sheets per year. The unit's energy is fully supplied by the gases from the steelmaking process. Its power plant and the high-pressure turbine of the blast furnace together have the capacity to generate 218 MW of electricity.

To optimize this activity in a recent plant, there was an investment of 1 billion reais in environmental processes and energy efficiency, and an industry benchmarking confirmed that CSP currently emits less than other market players.

Regarding economic and demographic data, São Gonçalo do Amarante has the 6th largest gross GDP in Ceará, among 184 cities, and the HDI is 0.665 (average), being the 13th in the state. The outstanding socioeconomic indicator is GDP per capita, which grew 11x in 10 years according to the IBGE.

This increase is closely associated with the port issue, which has been increasing its movement year after year. Having ended 2002 with 386,990 tons of cargo handled, in 2016 this figure reached 11,230,429, surpassing 10 million tons handled for the first time.

Ceará – Decarbonisation targets

The State of Ceará has been showing a large drop in emissions in recent years, accentuated in 2020 due to the Covid-19 pandemic, which greatly reduced emissions from the transport sector. The state of Ceará has been commissioning new renewable energy structures, mainly onshore wind, reducing emissions in the energy sector.

The State publicized in the media that it formulates the Ceará Green Plan, which will be a State Plan for a Fair Energy Transition, and should focus on green hydrogen, biofuels, and other renewable energy sources, following international guidelines. The full plan has not yet been published to the public.

The state announced that it believes in the decarbonisation of its economy as an instrument of social, economic, and environmental development. The plan is supported by the World Bank, an institution that will be a partner in technical assistance for the development, and production of green hydrogen in the state.

Figure 18 | GHG emissions in the State of Ceará - Brazil (1990-2020).
Source: (SEEG, 2021).

Green Hydrogen - The focus of the port of Pecém (Bezerra, 2021)

São Gonçalo do Amarante is being the stage for another technology under development to face the energy transition - green hydrogen. The port of Pecém will be the "green hydrogen hub" in Brazil, and is already developing pilot technologies, having received billions of investments.

The State of Ceará has been a pioneer in actions to consolidate a green hydrogen hub in Brazil and has already signed various protocols of intent between the State Government and international and national players interested in investing in the hydrogen production chain.

Several processes can produce hydrogen, and nomenclatures have been defined according to the different types of emissions, depending on the technology and energy source used, and with different cost implications and material requirements. Green hydrogen (renewable hydrogen) is produced by electrolysis, and electricity comes from renewable energy sources such as solar, wind and hydro.

Manaus - Amazonas

Carbon Capture and Storage

3,48
CO₂ capture potential

28,95%
Emissions local decrease

data in MtCO₂e, 2018.

Figure 19 | Dashboard of Manaus, Amazonas.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Manaus - Amazonas

Manaus is the capital of the state of Amazonas, being also the most populous city in that state, with 2,255,903 inhabitants (IBGE, 2021). This municipality is only the 4th largest emitter in the state of Amazonas, however, unlike other municipalities that have very high emissions due to deforestation of the Amazon Forest, Manaus has its emissions associated with the burning of power plants (SEEG, 2021). In emissions due to energy issues, Manaus is only behind the city of São Paulo, which is the most populous city with the greatest economic activity in Brazil.

Dependence on power plants, mainly natural gas, is a historical problem in Manaus and adjacent cities. The Amazon region has many physical difficulties to connect to the Brazilian national interconnected system (SIN), and Manaus was only connected to the system in 2013, still needing to expand this access in various parts of the municipality. The way to reduce power plants in this state is linked to adding more energy security to the region and avoiding the constant dispatch of power plants, but there is also potential in infrastructure for the CCS, since Manaus is a region with industrial developments, with gas pipelines that would help in transport.

Part of the dependence on power plants is associated with failed infrastructures in the region, such as the Balbina hydroelectric plant, inaugurated in 1980 and has until today the 5th largest installed generation capacity in Brazil, but which, due to sizing errors, delivers little energy and cannot meet the demand of Manaus and its surroundings (MORETTO, 2012).

Decarbonisation plans of Amazonas

Following the strategies of other Brazilian states, the state of Amazonas hired a multidisciplinary and international team to draw up decarbonisation routes aiming at Net Zero 2050.

The report "Pathways to Decarbonization", developed for the government of the State of Amazonas, was prepared by teams from the Climate Group, Winrock International, the Center for Climate Strategies and the Governors' Task Force on Forests and Climate. Seven areas were defined for priority actions, all associated with agriculture, forestry and other land uses (AFOLU), as seen below:

- Forest Protection.
- Efficiency in Land Use.
- Forest Expansion.
- Commercial reforestation.
- Reduction of Forest Burning.
- Sustainable Forest Management.
- Wood Forest Products.

The Amazonas state is comprised of a great extension of the Amazon biome, which increases the pressure to fight deforestation as a crucial world agenda. Therefore, energy or industrial decarbonisation plans are far from any role in the state.

BECCUS Potential by State

Source: IBGE, 2020; ANP, 2022.

Map 13 | Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage potential by state.

BECCUS Potential

Source: ANP, 2022; CIOTTA ET AL., 2021; EPE, 2018; IBGE, 2020.

Map 14 | Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage potential.

Uberaba - Minas Gerais (hub for BECCUS)

Figure 20 | Dashboard of Uberaba, Minas Gerais.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Uberaba - Minas Gerais (hub for BECCUS)

The municipality with the greatest potential for the development of BECCUS is Uberaba, located in the state of Minas Gerais.

In 2020, the city was the largest producer of sugarcane in Brazil, producing approximately 8 million tons of the product. 21.5% of the municipality's territory is occupied by sugar cane, and although there are several economic and technical benefits in the locality, which takes advantage of sugar cane in many ways, there are popular complaints about the burning of the plant, which is sometimes carried out before harvest (IBGE, 2021).

Uberaba has good infrastructure with access to railroads and gas pipelines, which would facilitate carbon storage.

The municipality has a carbon capture potential in the production of biofuels of 1,595 tCO₂/day and is authorized to produce 1,800 m³/day of anhydrous ethanol and 2,950 m³/day of hydrous ethanol. According to SEEG data from 2021, Uberaba was in 2019 the 8th municipality with the highest emissions of GHG in the state of Minas Gerais, and the 2nd that most emitted for activities related to Agriculture. Ethanol production through sugarcane is not mapped individually in Brazilian municipalities, and this emission is embedded in other activities, such as energy and agriculture.

The state of Minas Gerais has a decarbonisation plan carried out in partnership with the CDP (Carbon Disclosure Project). This document can be accessed in full here. In this document, this state defines its portfolio of possibilities to reach Net Zero 2050. BECCS and CCS are frequently cited as possibilities. BECCS is part of the possible portfolio for kerosene biofuels and diesel biofuels.

The excerpts below summarize the opportunities mapped by this report:

Diesel biofuel (BTL) CCS:

Fischer-Tropsch (FT) fuel plants offer a unique opportunity for carbon capture and storage (CCS). Synthesis gas is removed from the CO₂ during gas cleaning to increase the partial pressure of the reactants in the FT section. The resulting near-pure CO₂ stream from the Selexol unit process is easily captured for carbon storage, if desired.

Ethanol BECCUS:

During ethanol fermentation, sugars from conventional biofuel feedstocks are fermented into ethanol and CO₂. Two-thirds of the carbon contained in sugars ends up in ethanol; the remaining third forms almost pure CO₂. The CO₂ stream can then be separated by means of a gas-liquid separation, whereas the ethanol/water mixture is normally separated by distillation.

Mato Grosso - Cluster for BECCUS (3 Cities)

Local CO2 emission by sector (adding the 3 cities)

Population of the surroundings

Figure 21 | Dashboard of Mato Grosso.
Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Mato Grosso - Cluster for BECCUS (3 Cities)

A cluster of hubs in the State of Mato Grosso carry strong potential for the development of BECCUS. This cluster uniting the municipalities of **Sinop**, **Sorriso**, and **Lucas do Rio Verde** would be ideal due to the combined production potential that the cities have for biodiesel, anhydrous ethanol, or hydrous ethanol.

It turns out that despite the potential for biofuel production, the region does not have access to adequate infrastructure, such as gas pipelines or railways. The absence of these infrastructures is also a gap for secure carbon storage issues.

If the state of Mato Grosso adopts a policy of application of BECCS in its infrastructures, considering this cluster will be central for the state, since according to estimates from this study, 46.6% of all potential removals in that state would occur in these 3 municipalities, which have in total 141 cities. The carbon capture potential for BECCS in Mato Grosso calculated for the state is 11,000 tCO₂/day.

Mato Grosso - Possible first BECCS plant in Brazil

The city of Lucas do Rio Verde, one of the Hubs identified in this cluster, has the proposal to be the first location in Brazil that uses BECCS in its production. According to publications by the company FS Agri solutions Industria De Biocombustiveis Ltda (2021; 2022) on its website and in the media, the company has been carrying out geological and seismic studies to find a suitable location within a radius of up to 5 km from the production, to store carbon captured in its biofuel's activities.

According to FS (2022), the company units in Lucas do Rio Verde and Sorriso combined have the capacity to produce more than 1 billion liters of anhydrous ethanol per year. Ethanol is produced from corn, and the company holds the title of using 100% of corn in its units, whether producing ethanol, bioelectricity or for animal nutrition.

FS' long-term goal is for BECCS to help it become the first company in the world to produce ethanol with a negative carbon footprint, associated with other decarbonisation processes it practices.

Thus, the choice of the cluster is also associated with the location's potential for pioneering BECCS in Brazil.

CCS, BECCUS and the NDCs

The Paris Agreement is a legally binding international treaty signed in 2015 by 195 countries under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). The main aim of the Paris Agreement is to limit global warming to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels and to pursue efforts to limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C. To achieve this, the Paris Agreement sets out a framework for countries to progressively reduce their greenhouse gas emissions and to adapt to the impacts of climate change.

One of the key mechanisms of the Paris Agreement is the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). NDCs are the commitments that countries make to reduce their greenhouse gas emissions and to adapt to the impacts of climate change. These commitments are formulated and submitted by each country individually and are intended to reflect the specific circumstances and capabilities of each country. NDCs are reviewed and updated every five years, with the aim of increasing their level of ambition over time.

Among the countries that mention the CCS in their goals, we can mention:

- China: In its NDC, China committed to increasing the use of CCS as a means of reducing greenhouse gas emissions. The country has several CCS projects underway, including the GreenGen CCS project in Tianjin, which is capturing and storing up to 1 million tons of CO₂ per year.
- Norway: In its NDC, Norway committed to increasing the use of CCS as a means of reducing greenhouse gas emissions. The country has several CCS projects underway, including the Northern Lights CCS project, which is capturing and storing up to 1.5 million tons of CO₂ per year.
- United States: In its NDC, the United States committed to deploying CCS as part of its efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. The country has several CCS projects underway, including the Petra Nova CCS project in Texas, which is capturing and storing up to 1.6 million tons of CO₂ per year.

These are just a few examples of countries that have included CCS in their NDCs. It is worth noting that the specific commitments and targets related to CCS vary among countries, and some countries may have more advanced CCS programs than others.

CCS, BECCUS and the NDCs

In Brazil's case, according to the updated NDC at COP 29 in Baku in 2024, the country has plans to reduce its GHG emissions by 59 to 67 percent below 2005 levels by 2035. These targets will be achieved through a combination of measures, including increased use of renewable energy, improvements in energy efficiency, and efforts to reduce deforestation and promote reforestation.

The NDC does not specifically mention the use of CCS technologies as a means of reducing GHG emissions. However, in the energy sector, the National Climate Plan outlines the country's strategy to expand electricity generation while gradually replacing fossil fuels with electrification solutions and advanced biofuels over the medium to long term. A key component of this strategy is the promotion of biofuel production integrated with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) technologies to enable negative emissions. This approach reflects the recognition that carbon removals from the Land Use Change and Forestry sector alone will be insufficient to offset Brazil's residual emissions. Therefore, the development and deployment of CCS in conjunction with biofuels will be essential, depending on their economic viability and technological maturity in the coming decades.

This Report can help Brazil to make the use of BECCS and CCS to achieve its decarbonisation goals less abstract. There are several potential benefits to Brazil if it were to include clear goals for these technologies in its Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC).

These benefits could include:

- Reduction of GHG emissions: BECCS and CCS can help Brazil meet its GHG reduction targets set out in its NDC by capturing and storing CO₂ emissions from industrial and energy-related sources. This could help Brazil achieve its goal of reducing GHG emissions.
- Continued use of fossil fuels: Brazil is a major oil and natural gas producer. CCS could allow the country to continue using these resources while reducing its environmental impact.
- Economic benefits: BECCS and CCS technologies could create new jobs and economic opportunities in Brazil, as they would require the development and operation of new infrastructure, such as pipelines and storage facilities.
- Improved air quality: Reducing GHG emissions through CCS can also improve air quality by reducing the number of pollutants released into the atmosphere.

Overall, including BECCS and CCS in Brazil's NDC could help the country achieve its GHG reduction targets, continue to use fossil fuels while mitigating their environmental impact, create economic opportunities, and improve air quality.

Reflections for Brazil CCS deployment

As previously demonstrated, Brazil has the potential to develop and implement CCS/BECCUS projects in several sectors, such as the steel industry, cement, oil and gas refineries, etc. However, there are commercial and economic barriers that have prevented the large-scale implementation of carbon capture technologies in the country. Thus, the Figure 17 shows the prospects for the development of carbon capture in Brazil through a SWOT analysis.

Figure 22 | SWOT analysis for carbon capture deployment.
Source: Elaborated by the authors based on (NETTO et al., 2021).

Enabling Carbon Capture - Risk Analysis

Given its nature as an activity necessitating significant environmental and infrastructural alterations, carbon capture and storage (CCS) invariably emerges as a recurring theme in assessments of environmental risks and impacts. (BLACKFORD et al., 2020; KOORNNEEF et al., 2008). There are some works by international corporations that have assessed the geological risks for carbon storage, such as OSPAR (2007), the IEA GHG (2007), European Communities - EC (2008, 2011), CSA Group, (2012) and ISO ABNT, 2009.

In this line, Pontes et al. (2021) compiled the risks mapped by these and other institutions, providing an important panorama with the potential to assist in the management and assessment of risks associated with the process of geological stock of captured carbon. The table on the side shows this compilation.

The risk of CO₂ leakage in the reservoirs centralizes the risk analysis. In this sense, recent studies, such as by Blackford et al., (2020), showed that there are currently tools with high leak detectability, even in scenarios where the leak would have little impact. Analyzes such as that by Blackford et al., (2020), add to risk management, supporting detection for these activities.

Figure 23 | Stages of a framework for Risk Assessment of CO₂ storage streams in geological.

Source: PONTES et al. 2021.

Enabling Carbon Capture - Environmental Impact Assessment

Regarding the environmental issue, in Brazil there is a gap in the environmental licensing process for carbon storage, with no Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) protocol for these activities (MORETTO et al., 2018). The EIAs are broad processes, which in addition to making a thorough study of possible environmental impacts, also combine social and economic issues.

Faced with this gap, some studies have been developing approaches to face possible risks arising from this activity, such as initiating protocols that help in the development of this activity in Brazil. The Figure 24 shows a possible scheme to assess the environmental impact phases for the carbon capture and storage process.

Figure 24 | Environmental Impact Assessment of Carbon Capture and Storage – Phases

Source: MORETTO et al., 2018, p.7.

Enabling Carbon Capture - Environmental Impact Assessment

Many countries have already adopted their protocols for licensing CO₂ geological storage issues, such as the European Union, which requires an Environmental Impact Statement, in accordance with EU Directive 2009/31/EC amended in Annex I of EU Directive 85/337/EEC.

In Brazil, although there is no such detail, all projects considered technically as potentially causing significant environmental degradation in all circumstances require an Environmental Impact Statement for their Environmental Licensing (CONAMA, 1986).

Even so, the structure of the EIA (simplified or complete) and the Environmental Licensing for CO₂ Geological Storage Projects may vary depending on the geological characteristics of the storage site, or at different stages of its life cycle.

In this sense, the Figure 25 brings a study by DOOLEY et al., (2006), which precisely mapped the General type of geological CO₂ reservoirs, creating routes to think about possible environmental licensing, as well as the associated risks.

Figure 25 | General Characteristics of CO₂ Geological Reservoirs.

Source: DOOLEY et al., 2006.

Enabling CCS - Public Perception in Brazil

Public perception of carbon capture and storage (CCS) is a central factor in determining the viability of this technology. Local resistance can become a major barrier to its implementation. International experiences illustrate this dynamic: community support contributed to the success of projects like the CO₂CRC Otway Project in Australia and the FutureGen initiative in Mattoon, Illinois (ANDERSON et al., 2012), while local opposition led to the cancellation of the Barendrecht project in the Netherlands (CUPPEN et al., 2015; TERWEL et al., 2012; MASCARENHAS & MENEHINI, 2021).

In Brazil, the number of CCS initiatives remains limited, and there is a lack of in-depth studies focused on how local populations perceive the technology (NETTO et al., 2020; MASCARENHAS, 2022). In contrast, international literature has explored the social, cultural, and psychological factors that influence public acceptance or rejection of CCS (BUI et al., 2018; de BEST-WALDHOBBER et al., 2009; WADE & GREENBERG, 2009), especially in terms of how different communities assess risks and benefits.

Drawing on this gap, Netto et al. (2020) conducted a pioneering study in the Recôncavo Basin, Bahia — an area shaped by the presence of the oil industry. The research revealed that local history and identity, particularly connections to the oil sector, significantly influenced public attitudes toward CCS. Community empowerment emerged as a key variable, capable of positively or negatively shaping acceptance of new technologies. The study also emphasized the vital role of communication in correcting misconceptions and reducing distrust surrounding CCS.

A complementary study by Lima et al. (2021) surveyed 800 individuals in the Espírito Santo cities of São Mateus and Vitória. The findings showed a high level of concern about climate change—84% and 85% of respondents, respectively, acknowledged the issue. However, only a small fraction—2% and 5%—considered investments in climate mitigation a top priority. Most participants prioritized health, public safety, and job creation. This disconnect illustrates the complexity of public attitudes: while climate change is recognized as a serious issue, more immediate social needs often take precedence. The authors concluded that broader public engagement and improved information about CCS are needed to better connect the technology with local development priorities.

Enabling CCS - Public Perception in Brazil

Synthesizing these findings, Mascarenhas (2022) underscores several key insights: although there is general support for climate action in Brazil, CCS remains a low public priority. Scepticism persists, coupled with low willingness to pay for emission-reducing technologies—partly due to financial constraints, lack of information, and a perception that responsibility lies with the government or industry. Trust in project developers, familiarity with the oil and gas sector, and a sense of social justice in economically vulnerable areas are crucial factors that influence acceptance. In regions marked by inequality and low educational attainment, CCS projects may be more welcome when framed around job creation and economic opportunity. However, poorly managed engagement can lead to NIMBY ("Not In My Back Yard") reactions, especially if risks are perceived or community trust is lacking.

Public perception is also highly sensitive to **contextual factors**, such as past exposure to environmental stress, natural disasters, or prior experience with large infrastructure projects. Perceived **risks** include CO₂ leakage, air and water contamination, seismic activity, soil infertility, and road damage. Communities also note **benefits** such as employment, royalties, and local economic development (MASCARENHAS, 2022). Moreover, public views tend to be more critical of **onshore CCS projects**, while **offshore** initiatives may attract less attention—though international cases like Tomakomai, Japan, (MABON et al., 2017) show that even marine-based CCS can raise concerns among coastal communities, such as fishers and the seafood industry (MASCARENHAS, 2022).

Regulatory clarity and public trust are both essential to the success of future CCS initiatives. Financing models must also be evaluated, including scenarios where consumers might contribute—raising questions about willingness to pay and preferences among low-carbon technologies (MASCARENHAS, 2022).

Current research tends to rely on quantitative methods like surveys, often conducted by experts from engineering or natural sciences (SOVACOOOL, 2014). While useful, such tools may fail to capture the complex, collective, and emotional dimensions of public attitudes. Insights from behavioural and social sciences are needed to move beyond identifying *what* people think toward understanding *why*, *how*, and *under what conditions* perceptions are formed and evolve (MASCARENHAS, 2022).

In this light, interdisciplinary research approaches that incorporate psychology, sociology, and political science are essential. Social perception is not static; it emerges from dynamic interactions between beliefs, values, social norms, emotions, and identities. These elements evolve in feedback loops between individuals, communities, and institutions—especially under conditions of uncertainty and controversy, such as those surrounding climate change (MASCARENHAS, 2022).

This understanding is central to the ongoing research at the Research Centre for Greenhouse Gas Innovation (RCGI), which seeks to explore these deeper dynamics to support more inclusive and effective pathways for Brazil's low-carbon transition.

Conclusion

A study utilizing geographic layer overlays enabled the aggregation of multiple strata with decision-making potential for Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) in the Brazilian territory. This analysis identified three potential locations for CCS deployment and two for Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS). It is important to note that this report was produced between 2022 and 2023, and the information has not been updated since.

This sociogeographical study demonstrated its effectiveness, validating the methodological approach used to identify regions suitable for further feasibility assessments. It also highlighted the need for complementary studies—such as public perception analyses—to better understand local responses to these emerging technologies. Given Brazil's ongoing challenges with infrastructure development, the first two proposed CCS hubs—Serra and São Gonçalo do Amarante—share key characteristics: proximity to ports, economies driven by steel production, and access to oil wells as potential CO₂ storage sites.

These regions, which experienced rapid economic and/or population growth following the introduction of industrial infrastructure, also exhibit notable socio-environmental challenges. Infrastructure remains a defining factor in the selection of the third CCS hub: the city of Manaus. With a complex history of development policies and mixed outcomes, Manaus—the capital of Amazonas—possesses the basic framework to support CCS initiatives. However, the city's reliance on poorly planned hydroelectric projects and fossil fuel-based power plants has made it a significant emitter of greenhouse gases, further emphasizing the urgency for targeted climate solutions in the region.

For BECCS, we identified a very diffuse pattern of biofuel production in Brazil, which supports the need for complementary studies to define clusters by grouping some of the hubs found. This addendum can be decisive, as the state of São Paulo — which showed the greatest potential for BECCS — had no hubs detected in the methodology precisely due to the dispersed nature of its production.

The main hub for BECCS was the mining town of Uberaba, Brazil's largest sugarcane producer. The second-highest potential for BECCS was observed in a cluster of three cities in Mato Grosso, a biodiesel production center using corn — highlighting the diversity of biofuel sources in Brazil. We found that significant challenges remain, particularly regarding environmental licensing and public acceptance of such projects. On the environmental front, the literature has made considerable progress in identifying correlations with similar national projects, especially in the oil industry, and with international regulations, to suggest viable protocols for carbon geological storage in Brazil.

Regarding public perception, international literature emphasizes the importance of contextualizing social issues, as they are central to the viability of these and other decarbonization technologies. Few studies in Brazil indicate that the association of technology with climate change mitigation is still a less prominent topic than more immediate local benefits, such as job and income generation. Moreover, public perception studies related to carbon capture and storage remain very scarce in Brazil, representing a significant scientific gap.

Therefore, by identifying potential hubs for CCS and BECCS, this work aims to support future public perception surveys aligned with the direction provided by the proposed model.

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Annex: Methodological step-by-step – QGIS (CCS)

1. Collect SEEG emissions data by activity and municipality <<https://plataforma.seeg.eco.br/cities/statistics>>.
2. Process data for mt¹ of the following activities: Cement; Electricity; Metallurgy and Fuel Production - activities with the greatest potential for implementing CCS (bibliometric analysis of CCS).
3. Treat data from the supplementary material of the article “CO₂ storage potential of offshore oil and gas fields in Brazil” (change the lines in the Field column to capital letters) <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2021.103492>>.
4. Download shapefiles of production fields, sedimentation basins and gas pipelines (infrastructure) from GeoANP: <<http://geo.anp.gov.br/mapview>>.
5. Start a blank project in Qgis.
6. Incorporate data from the IBGE Geopackage: <<https://www.ibge.gov.br/geociencias/cartas-e-mapas/bases-cartograficas-continuas/15759-brasil.html?=&t=downloads>> Layers a to be incorporated into the project: railway section and limit of municipalities by polygons.
7. Add GeoANP shapes.
8. Enter the CSVs of the fields' emissions and storage data.

9. Create a raster figure with the location of the gas pipelines. To do this: Process Toolbox >> GDAL >> Vector Conversion >> Convert Vector to Raster (raterize). In the dialog fill in the following attributes:

- Input Layer: Pipelines.
- Fixed value to burn: 1.00.
- Output size units: Pixels.
- Horizontal/Width Resolution: 2000.00.
- Vertical Resolution/Height: 2000.00.
- Output extension: select the Counties polygon.
- Assign a value of “no data” ...: Not defined.
- Additional creation options >> Profile: No compression.
- Rasterized: choose a path to save the file.

10. Do step 9 for the railway vector.

11. Merge the fields Field (storage data csv) and NOM_CAMPO from the production fields shape.

12. Treat the Fields layer by creating a new field called Storage. Storage should be a copy of the 50% storage column from the Carbon Storage csv but showing integers (Int).

13. Repeat step 9 with the Fields polygon

¹ This step is important for creating heat maps. If it is left in emission units (tCO₂e) the points take time and Qgis will hang in the procedure.

Annex: Methodological step-by-step – QGIS (CCS)

14. Merge the geocode fields of the emission data layers and cities by points (in the municipalities layer).

15. Treat the Municipalities (municipalities) layer by creating fields for cement, energy, metallurgy, other energy and refinery. The new fields should be copies of the Carbon Emissions csv data column, but with integers (Int) colored upwards

16. Repeat step 9 for each emission source, changing Output Size Units to Pixels and Resolutions to 10000.00.

- The. Input Layer: counties.
- Field to use as burn-in value: Desired emissions column
- Fixed value to burn: Not defined.
- Output size units: Pixels.
- and. Horizontal/Width Resolution: 10000.00.
- Vertical Resolution/Height: 10000.00.
- Output extension: select the Counties polygon.
- Assign a value of “no data” ...: Not defined.
- Additional creation options >> Profile: No compression.
- Rasterized: choose a path to save the file.

17. Convert the Fields polygon layer into points (Vector >> Geometries >> Centroids...).

18. Layer projector for SIRGAS 2000 / 23 S

19. Create a heatmap with the storage capacity of the fields (Toolbox >> Interpolation >> Heatmap (choose 100m radius, Quartic and Scaled).

20. Add the rasters, with the raster calculator tool, thus creating the Capture_and_Storage layer.

21. Cut the raster using the Counties polygon layer as a mask.

Annex: Methodological step-by-step – QGIS (BECCUS)

1. Retrieve authorization data for biofuel production: <https://www.gov.br/anp/pt-br/assuntos/producao-e-fornecimento-de-biocombustiveis/autorizacao-para-producao-de-biocombustiveis>. Data are geospatial, with the amount of authorization per Brazilian municipality for the production of biodiesel (m³/d), biogas (Nm³/d), anhydrous ethanol (m³/d) and hydrous ethanol (m³/d);

2. Calculate carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions based on the amount of authorization for biofuel production, considering the following emission factors (EF):

The. Emission of 426.1 gCO₂/kg for the production of biodiesel (source: Emprapa, 2014; <https://www.infoteca.cnptia.embrapa.br/bitstream/doc/987401/1/Doc334online.pdf>);

B. Emission of 330 kgCO₂/m³ for the production of hydrous ethanol (same source as above).

c. Emission of 345 kgCO₂/m³ for the production of anhydrous ethanol (same source as above).

d. For biogas, it was considered that 40% of the energy source composition is composed of CO₂ (source: Rosa et al., 2021; DOI: 10.1039/d1ee00642h), requiring its elimination to use biomethane. In this way, CO₂ would be captured instead of being eliminated in the atmosphere, thus negatively impacting emissions from the biomethane production process (source: Rosa et al., 2021; DOI: 10.1039/d1ee00642h).

The following equation demonstrates the potential for CO₂ capture in the production of biofuels in Brazil, remembering that the potential was calculated for each Brazilian municipality:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{[[BECCUS]]_pot} &= \text{Prod.Biodiesel} \times \text{[[FE]]_Biodiesel} \\ &+ \text{Prod.Etanol anhydrous} \times \text{[[FE]]_Etanol anhydrous} \\ &+ \text{Prod.Etanol hydrous} \times \text{[[FE]]_Etanol hydrous} \\ &+ \text{Prod.Biomethano} \times 40\% \end{aligned}$$

It was necessary to consider the densities of biodiesel (about 0.90 g/cm³, source: <https://aprobio.com.br/noticia/biodiesel-e-suas-propriedades>) and CO₂ (about 1.98 kg/ m³, source: <http://www.gamagases.com.br/propriedades-dos-gases-dioxido-de-carbono.html>)

3. Insert the data in the Qgis project and merge with the municipalities layer.

4. Convert vectorized layer to raster figure, repeating step 9 of the procedure for calculating the CCS potential.

5. Perform step 20 of the procedure for calculating the CCS potential, considering weight 1 for the potential BECCUS layer, weight 100 for the storage layer and weight 1,000 for the transport layers (empirical methodology, otherwise these values of weight the result for greater potential would be municipalities in the interior of MT, without any access to infrastructure, that is, without access to gas pipelines or even railroads);

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